

Implementation of the Fast Total Monte Carlo Method for Uncertainty Quantification in Rod Withdrawal Transient Simulations

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ABSTRACT

Uncertainty quantification for time dependent simulations has traditionally relied on deterministic codes due to the high computational cost of the Monte Carlo method. However, with increasing computational power, traditional random sampling based uncertainty quantification methods have also been applied for Monte Carlo simulations, including faster methods, such as Fast Total Monte Carlo. So far the faster methods have been mainly used for steady state simulations. This paper attempts to quantify nuclear data uncertainty in a prompt supercritical transient Monte Carlo simulation. The rod withdrawal scenario of the TMI mini-core benchmark was used as the test case, with the impact of the number of neutrons released per ²³⁵U fission on the core power and reactivity being computed using the Fast Total Monte Carlo method and the Total Monte Carlo method, the latter being considered as reference. In general, good agreement was observed between the two methods, with the fast method decreasing the computational time by an order of magnitude. In the case of the core power evolution, both methods showed a clear increase in the uncertainty due to nuclear data from approximately 2.0 % to 4.5 % during the transient. In the case of the reactivity, a reduction of the uncertainty was observed during the transient for both methods, converging towards ~4.0 %. However, in this case, large variances and unphysical behaviours in the uncertainty were observed when using the Fast Total Monte Carlo method, which will require further studies. Nevertheless, the implementation of the fast method shows promise for transient Monte Carlo simulations.

Keywords: uncertainty quantification, transient, Fast Total Monte Carlo, TMI mini-core

1. INTRODUCTION

Uncertainty quantification (UQ) is an important aspect for reactor safety. It allows nuclear physicists to analyse how uncertainties in parameters such as input data, manufacturing tolerances and measurement error affect reactor performance. Within the nuclear community one of the main UQ method used is the Total Monte Carlo (TMC) method. This straightforward brute-force approach requires performing hundreds of simulations, each with perturbed input parameters sampled from their respective probability density functions. While the method scales well with a large number of uncertain parameters, it requires a significant number of samples to reach convergence in the statistical uncertainty of the quantity of interest.

Compared to deterministic neutronics codes, Monte Carlo simulations are frequently hailed as the "golden standard" within reactor physics, and therefore using Monte Carlo UQ methods for Monte Carlo simulations is appealing, albeit computationally expensive. There have been successful attempts made to quantify uncertainties for steady state simulations, including the development of faster UQ methods such as the Fast Total Monte Carlo (Fast TMC) and the Fast GRS method, as discussed in Ref [1], [2], and [3]. In this paper, we extended this approach by applying the Fast TMC method on a

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transient Monte Carlo simulation, and comparing the results to those obtained by the TMC method, considered as reference. More specifically, we explored the impact of the uncertainty in nuclear data on the core power and reactivity evolution during a control rod withdrawal simulation.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. TMI Mini-core

For our investigation into uncertainty quantification for transients, we modelled a control rod withdrawal. We used the TMI mini-core benchmark as a test case, shown in Figure 1 [4]. This core consists of a square lattice of 3x3 fuel assemblies. Each assembly is made up of a combination of 4.85 wt% enriched UO_2 fuel pins (pink), Gd-UO_2 with 4.12 wt% enriched uranium burnable poison (purple) pins, an instrumentation tube (yellow) and several guide tubes (white) in a lattice of 15x15 pins. The guide tubes contain AgInCd control rods in the central assembly and are empty in the surrounding assemblies. This 3x3 assembly core is surrounded by light water which acts as a reflector. A fuel temperature of 551 K and core power of 2.772 MW_{th} were considered [5].

Figure 1. TMI Fuel Assembly Geometry [4]

2.2. Transient Simulation with TMI

We used the 3D neutron transport code Serpent 2 to perform the transient simulations. Transient simulations are performed in two steps. In the first step, a critical steady state simulation is performed and the distribution of the prompt neutrons are saved at tentative collision sites and at random points during their lifetime based on a probability inversely proportional to their collision frequency [6]. The precursor distribution is based on their production rates in a critical core. These distributions are then used as the external source for the second step, the actual transient. To ensure that the core is critical at the start of the transient, the neutron production and reactions are scaled directly in Serpent by the k_{eff} of the steady state run.

For this study we simulated a rod withdrawal transient. During 1 second, the control rod assembly was extracted by 40 cm, introducing approximately 224 pcm of reactivity into the core, making it prompt supercritical. A total of 1.5 seconds was simulated over 56 time steps, with the rod movement taking place between 0.3 and 1.3 s. Smaller time intervals of 0.02 s were defined during the rod withdrawal to more accurately model the movement, and time steps of 0.1 s were used for the rest of the simulation.

At each time step neutron population control techniques were applied to ensure that the population did not grow unbounded and the tallies needed for the analysis were recorded.

We were interested in the power and neutron population evolution at each time step during the time dependent simulation. The evolution of the core power is straightforward and it is determined from a single tally. However, Serpent 2 does not explicitly calculate the core reactivity ρ at each time step thus the inverse point kinetics equation, presented in Eq. 1, is used to compute it [7]. This method relies on a single time dependent neutron population tally, $n(t)$, and the kinetic parameters: the prompt neutron generation time Λ , the delayed neutron fractions β_i , and the decay constants λ_i .

$$\rho(t) = \frac{\Lambda}{n(t)} \frac{dn(t)}{dt} + \beta - \frac{n(0)}{n(t)} \sum \beta_i e^{-\lambda_i t} - \frac{1}{n(t)} \sum \beta_i \lambda_i e^{-\lambda_i t} \int_0^t e^{\lambda_i x} n(x) dx \quad (1)$$

The kinetic parameters are calculated during the transient run, however, since they are calculated from the iterated fission probability method based on asymptotic populations [8], the steady state results are more accurate and precise. We looked at the impact of the control rod position on the values of the kinetic parameters and they were negligible. So the steady state values can be used during the analysis of the transient.

The neutron population tallies are taken at discrete time steps during the transient simulation. Therefore, the derivative and integral in Eq. 1 are evaluated numerically. To calculate the statistical uncertainty of ρ , a set of neutron population is sampled based on the tallied $n(t)$ value and its 1σ uncertainty at each time step assuming a normal distribution. The same method is also used to propagate the kinetic parameters. From this set of population and kinetic parameters, a corresponding set of reactivity values is calculated using Eq. 1. The standard deviation in these reactivity values is taken as the statistical uncertainty of ρ at the given timestep.

2.3. Uncertainty Quantification with Monte Carlo Methods

As a reference we used the Total Monte Carlo UQ method. Assume we are interested in the impact the input parameter A has on the calculated quantity q . Suppose a unique Monte Carlo simulation $C(m)$ takes T seconds and m histories to get a sufficiently small statistical uncertainty σ_{stat} on quantity q . The TMC method states that by repeating this simulation n times with the same seed but different (perturbed) input parameter A_i , the uncertainty caused by said input parameter σ_A can be calculated with Eq. 2 [9], and the total observed uncertainty σ_{tot} and the statistical uncertainty σ_{stat} can be calculated with Eq. 3 and 4 respectively [9]. In the case of a transient simulation, these uncertainties are computed at each time step.

$$\sigma_{tot}^2 \approx \overline{\sigma_{stat}^2} + \sigma_A^2(q) \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{tot}^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (q_i - \bar{q})^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\overline{\sigma_{stat}^2} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{stat,i}^2 \quad (4)$$

This method requires a total simulation time of $n \times T$ s to obtain the desired σ_A . However, having to repeat the simulation n times makes this method less appealing for longer simulations. Hence, a faster method was developed at NRG [9] aptly named the Fast TMC method. This method still uses n number of runs, like the TMC method, but each run has a different seed s_i and a significantly lower number, m/n , of histories. Different seeds were used to get statistically distinct and uncorrelated runs. Due to the lower number of histories, these simulations finish quicker at the cost of statistical precision. Since equations 2-4 still hold, the same results can be obtained within T s instead of $n \times T$ s. Uncertainties can therefore be calculated within the time it takes for a single run to complete. The Fast TMC method have been successfully applied for steady state simulations in the past [9].

Both the TMC and Fast TMC method rely on using a large sample of perturbed input data. For this study, SANDY (SAmpler of Nuclear Data and uncertaintyY) [10] was used to perturb the ^{235}U nuclear

data and create 400 samples. The same set of samples were used for both the TMC and Fast TMC methods. All nuclear data was taken from the JEFF3.3 nuclear data library [11]. The main simulation parameters are summarized in Table I. These parameters ensured that the statistical uncertainties in the neutron population tallies in the Fast TMC runs were on average $\sim 4\%$, which is sufficient for our transient simulations.

Table I. Simulation parameters for the TMC and Fast TMC runs.

	TMC	Fast TMC
Neutron Population	1.0×10^7	6.0×10^5
Batch Size	1.0×10^4	5.0×10^4
Seed	Same	Random
Sample number	400	400

3. RESULTS

3.1. Sensitivity Analysis

As a first step, we performed an initial sensitivity study with Serpent 2 for the steady state TMI mini-core to determine which parameter has the largest effect on the multiplication factor. This study was focused on the ^{235}U nuclear data. Figure 2 shows the sensitivity of the multiplication factor k_{eff} to the main cross sections, and the fission spectrum (χ), and the number of neutrons released per fission event (nubar) for ^{235}U . For these calculations, the standard 172 group XMAS energy grid was used. As it can be seen, the ^{235}U nubar has the largest impact on the multiplication factor of the TMI mini-core, and thus it was chosen as the parameter to perturb.

Figure 2. Sensitivity of the k_{eff} to the ^{235}U cross sections, χ , and nubar; the standard 172 group XMAS energy grid was used

In order to define the number of samples needed to reach convergence, we looked at the evolution of the average statistical uncertainty in the reactivity at the first time step of the transient with increasing number of samples. The results, depicted in Figure 3, show that 400 samples were sufficient to reach convergence in the uncertainty for both the TMC (blue) and Fast TMC (orange) methods for transient simulations.

Figure 3. Average statistical uncertainty in the reactivity at the first time step as a function of the number of simulated samples for the TMC (blue) and Fast TMC (orange) methods; Arrows indicate which y-axis belongs to which curve

3.2. Uncertainty Quantification

The impact of nuclear data uncertainty on the core power and reactivity evolution during a transient is presented in the following sections.

On average, a single transient simulation took 30 hours for the TMC and ~2.7 hours for the Fast TMC method; representing a ~90% decrease in computational time when using the Fast TMC method.

3.2.1. Power evolution

We compare the evolution of the core power for each of the 400 TMC and Fast TMC runs with the reference run: a transient simulation without perturbed nuclear data. This is presented in Figure 4 with the reference run in black, TMC in blue and Fast TMC in orange. The red dashed lines indicate the period of rod movement.

Figure 4. Core power evolution for the reference (black) and for each TMC (blue) and Fast TMC (orange) run; Red dashed lines indicate rod movement period

Both the TMC and Fast TMC runs accurately model the core power up to 1 second into the transient, after which both methods show a larger power than the reference. However, the reference power is still within the spread of runs from both methods. Additionally, as expected, the spread in the values is

larger for the Fast TMC runs due to the higher statistical uncertainties resulting from the lower neutron population.

Using Eq. 2-4, we computed the uncertainty in the core power for each time step and method. The results are shown in Figure 5, where the relative uncertainty in the core power due to nuclear data for the TMC (blue circle) and Fast TMC (orange square) methods is depicted. As it can be observed, the results obtained with the two methods are in good agreement throughout the transients, with the results of the Fast TMC method oscillating around the reference TMC results. Overall it can be observed that the nuclear data uncertainty increases during the transient, from $\sim 2.0\%$ to $\sim 4.5\%$, equivalent to approximately 0.05 MW and 0.18 MW respectively.

Figure 5. Relative uncertainty in the core power due to nuclear data computed with the TMC (blue circle) and Fast TMC (orange square) methods; Red dashed lines indicate rod movement period

3.2.2. Reactivity evolution

The evolution of the reactivity in the reference run (black) and for each of the 400 TMC (blue) and Fast TMC (orange) runs is shown on Figure 6. This time dependent reactivity is calculated from the single neutron population tally using Eq. 1.

Figure 6. Core reactivity evolution for the reference (black) and for each TMC (blue) and Fast TMC (orange) run; Red dashed lines indicate rod movement period

The reference run in Figure 6 is fully contained within the TMC and Fast TMC runs. Similar to the power evolution, both methods are accurate from the start of the transient until about 1 second. After 1 second, both methods tend to overestimate the reference.

The relative nuclear data uncertainty for both the TMC (blue circle) and Fast TMC (orange square) methods are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Relative nuclear data uncertainty with the TMC (blue circle) and Fast TMC (orange square) methods; Red dashed lines indicate rod movement period

From Figure 7 we notice three interesting features. The first is a reduction in the relative uncertainty in the reactivity due to nuclear data as the transient progresses. This is opposite what we observe for the power evolution. During the transient, the relative uncertainty converges towards $\sim 4.0\%$ (~ 9.5 pcm) for both methods. This $\sim 4.0\%$ value is comparable to the relative uncertainty in the power at the end of the transient. The second observation is the $\sim 57\%$ relative uncertainty before the transient. This is likely due to the near 0 reactivity before the transient which results in a disproportionately larger relative uncertainty. Large uncertainty values are also observed with the Fast TMC method slightly after the start of the transient at ~ 0.4 s. As reactivity is added to the core, the relative contribution of the nuclear data uncertainty decreases, leading to the overall trend seen. Finally, it can also be observed that several Fast TMC data points are missing from the plot. At these time steps, the statistical uncertainty was larger than the total uncertainty. This is unphysical and makes it impossible to calculate the nuclear data uncertainty with Eq. 2. This was not observed for the power or neutron population tallies. Therefore, our results, in particular our reactivity results, can be unreliable if we cannot guarantee that the statistical uncertainty is much smaller than the nuclear data one. However, this would require increasing the simulated neutron population, effectively reducing the advantage of the Fast TMC method. Further exploration needs to be performed before definitive conclusions can be drawn.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We attempted to quantify the impact of the uncertainty in the ^{235}U fission multiplication factor on the core power and reactivity evolution during a rod withdrawal Monte Carlo transient using the Total Monte Carlo and the Fast Total Monte Carlo methods. Both methods have already been successfully applied for steady state cases. In the case of the studied transient, the results obtained with the Fast TMC method have been compared with the results obtained with TMC method, which was considered as the reference. One of the main motivations behind using the Fast TMC as a UQ method was the overall reduction in the simulation runtime, which is significantly higher for a transient run than a steady-state run, and for which TMC method can be cumbersome.

For our analysis we focused on the uncertainty propagation to the core power and reactivity. The time dependent power tallies were taken directly from Serpent 2, whereas reactivity was calculated using the inverse point kinetics method from the time dependent neutron population tallies. Overall, we

observed a relatively good agreement between the methods for both the power and reactivity results, with the Fast TMC methodology reducing the total computation time by a factor of 10. In the case of the power evolution, we observed an increase in the uncertainty due to the nuclear data from 2 % (0.05 MW) at the start of the transient to ~4.5 % (~0.18 MW) at the end.

Regarding the uncertainty on the reactivity, we observed that the relative uncertainty is decreasing throughout the transient, converging to ~4.0 % (~9.5 pcm), comparable to the value we obtained in the case of the power. We also noticed several unexpected results in the case of the uncertainty in the reactivity: over 50 % uncertainty values at certain time steps for the Fast TMC method, and a larger statistical uncertainty than total uncertainty at certain other time steps, which is unphysical. This leads to unreliable results particularly if we cannot guarantee that the statistical uncertainty is much smaller than the nuclear data one. Further investigation is still needed. Regardless of this obstacle, the Fast TMC method shows potential in accurately determining uncertainty in transient simulations in a fraction of the computation time needed for the TMC method.

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